

ISic4398

I.Sicily inscription 4398

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

mosaic

Object

mosaic

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halicyae

Place of origin (modern)

Salemi

Provenance

most northerly epigraphic panel of mosaic/basilica B, in the paleo-Christian basilica first excavated by Salinas in 1893

Coordinates

37.833019, 12.808066

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Salemi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

tessillis

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Ζώσιμος

Apparatus

Text of Bilotta via SEG 36.830

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285073

EDR 108402

PHI 331390

Bibliography

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1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 36.0830

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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Rizzone, V.G. 2011. Opus Christi edificabit: stati e funzioni dei cristiani di Sicilia attraverso l'apporto dell'epigrafia (secoli IV-VI). *Documenti e studi di Synaxis* 25. Troina. At 307 H13

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